

Innovation

**Innovation Conceptualization and Innovation New Models
Theoretical Summary**

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Foreword

The paper was prepared for the European Commission, Directorate General Information Society (DG INFSO) unit C3, as a stage research on the innovation paradigm.

The study is of the conceptual and summary nature. It researches some of the innovation theory evolution aspects, particularly stressing the importance of the (new) innovation concept model, which is connected with the knowledge accumulation and knowledge network exchange. Paper brings an example of the Open Source as an example of modern innovation creation model.

Study is divided into eight logically connected chapters. First and the second chapter introduce the innovation definition frameworks and innovation process concept. Third and fourth chapter introduce network theory through and particularly Open Source model example. Fifth and Sixth chapters concern innovation measurement and particularly new set of indicators. Last chapter describes possible innovation impact on the economy growth through the transmission mechanisms and increased productivity factors.

The author is aware of the broadness and complicity of the subject. It is often impossible to compare innovation paradigm between the sectors of the economy, and therefore further more focused analysis should be made in order to precise the findings.

The paper is a draft and it is still under construction.

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1. Definition of the Innovation

As early as 1911, J. Schumpeter¹ in his work on economic development distinguished between five different types of innovation:

- new products
- new methods of production
- new sources of supply
- the exploration of new market
- new ways to organize business

Most of the definitions focus on the first two of these: *new products* and *methods of production (processes)* as the most distinctive in the economic analysis of the innovation.

The argument for focusing particularly on the product and process innovation often rests on the assumption that their economic and social impact may differ. While the introduction of “new product” is commonly assumed to have a clear, positive effect on growth of income and employment, it has been argued that process innovation, due to its cost-cutting nature, may have more ambiguous effect.²

In accordance with the communication of the European Commission COM (1995) 688 (Green Paper on Innovation), consistent with the Lisbon European Council’s perception of the innovation and competitiveness, innovation is defined as: “*the renewal and enlargement of the range of products and services and associated markets; the establishment of new methods of production, supply and distribution; the introduction in changes in management, work organization, and the working conditions and skills of workforce.*”³

Even broader definition was introduced in the most recent European Commission innovation policy communication⁴ i.e.: “innovation is the successful production, assimilation and exploitation of novelty in economic and social spheres”.

¹ Schumpeter, J. (1934), *The Theory of Economic Development*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

² Fagerberg Jan (2004), *The Oxford Handbook of Innovation*, Chapter 1: A guide to the Literature, Oxford University Press, Oxford, New York

³ COM (1995) 688

⁴ COM (2003) 112 final

These two definitions continue to be a valid basis for Commission's approach towards innovation policy, but have very broad character and are not always proper for quantitative measurement purposes.

For the statistical and measurement purpose the harmonised innovation definition was introduced. The definition was proposed in the guidelines for collecting and interpreting technological innovation data (Oslo Manual) by OECD, European Commission (DG Competition) and Eurostat:⁵ *“Technological product and process (TPP) innovations comprise implemented technologically new products and processes and significant technological improvements in products and processes. A TPP innovation has been implemented if it has been introduced on the market (product innovation) or used within a production process (process innovation). TPP innovations involve a series of scientific, technological, organisational, financial and commercial activities. The TPP innovating firm is one that has implemented technologically new or significantly technologically improved products or processes during the period under review.”*

The Technological Product and Process (TPP) definition creates a framework for all the legal innovation definitions in the EU states. The definition narrows the innovation to the technological its concept. It excludes organisational and managerial innovations as hard to measure in quantitative terms. Appendix I shows its main features as to the OECD's approach towards defining TPP non TPP innovation and non innovative processes.

Despite the existence of harmonised innovation definition the Commission in some cases uses the broader definition, which embraces also managerial and non-technological innovation (purely organisational) – connected to the process innovation. Such definition was used in the Innovation Scoreboard 2004⁶ (Appendix I).

The Community Innovation Survey conducted in 2004, for defining scope and impact of technological innovation and innovation activity of enterprise uses *a contrario* definition (Appendix II) i.e. defining what innovation processes are not. The appendix introduces a schematic summary of the Oslo Manual TPP innovation. The cross-organizational definition comparison framework is shown in the Appendix IV of the study.

⁵ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

⁶ SEC (2004) 1475

2. Theoretical aspects of the innovation – innovation as a process

The claim that innovation plays a significant role in economic development and growth mechanisms is not a new one. It goes as far as Adam Smith (1776) and Joseph Schumpeter (1911) works. In the period of industrial and information revolution the significance and understanding of innovation evolved.⁷ Appendix V gives a glance on the evolution aspects in the innovation concept.

When in the 1911, Joseph Schumpeter published for the first time “The theory of Economic Development”,⁸ he described the motor of the development as the innovation itself. The innovation was not well defined by that time but it was clearly described in his proceeding works in which he used the innovation term.

According to Peter Drucker, J. Schumpeter was the economist who focused his studies on the entrepreneurship and its impact on the economy. The norm for the healthy economy and basis for its theory and practice should not be balance and optimisation but dynamic imbalance caused by the innovation implementing enterprises. This temporary imbalance is seen as the only way of economic development. Development is created by the “*creative destruction*”, by temporary destruction of balance.⁹

There exists a dichotomy in the innovation creation process model: linear (traditional model) and network (interactive) or chain link model (known a feedback model). According to linear model concept, starting impulse for the innovation processes is given by research followed by development, production phase and market implementation.

But the vector of the innovation process spin can and should be stimulated in the reverse direction. The innovation, as it creation is economic one, should be created based on the market target. There is a big concern in nowadays analysis towards the entrepreneurship-based innovation and market oriented research and development.¹⁰ Linear market oriented (innovation pull model) is shown on the figure below.

⁷ ERASME laboratory (2004), A 3 % R&D effort in Europe in 2010: an analysis of the consequences, using the Nemesis model

⁸ Schumpeter, J. (1934), *The Theory of Economic Development*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

⁹ Drucker Peter. F. (1985), *Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, Harper and Row, New York

Figure 1
Linear innovation model

Source: Rothwell R. Gardiner P. (1983), *The Role of Design in Product and Process Change*, Design Studies, 3

Linear model explains only innovation creation process within big integrated projects managed by big corporations or government bodies. The majority of the innovation project is created differently. According to Drucker's theory it has to be market oriented and if it is product oriented it will create a "technology miracle" without creating required benefits.¹¹

Peter Drucker stressed that "innovation is not a linear process" and in most cases it can be an irrational process. J. Schumpeter also stressed non static character of the development which is not likely to arise from schematic mechanisms and optimised, balanced processes.¹² This assumption was confirmed later in so-called chain-link model, which creates a basic framework in the innovation network analysis.

Kline and Rosenberg¹³ confirmed, through this model that innovation process rests on the three basic aspects:

1. innovation is not a sequential (linear) process but one involving many interactions and feedbacks in knowledge creation.
2. innovation is a learning process involving multiple inputs
3. innovation does not depend on invention process (in the sense of discovery of new principles), and such processes (involving formal R&D) tend to be undertaken as problem solving within an ongoing innovation process rather than an initiating factor

¹⁰ Allot Stephen (2005), *People Not Ideas*, Prospect, April 2005

¹¹ Drucker Peter F. (1974), *Management. Tasks, Responsibilities, Practices*, Harper & Row

¹² Schumpeter, J. (1934), *The Theory of Economic Development*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

¹³ Kline S. and Rosenberg N (1986), *What is behind the recent surge in patenting*, Research Policy 28

Figure 2
Chain-link model of the innovation
describes relation between research, innovation and production

Source: Kline S. J., Rosenberg N., (1986), *An Overview of Innovation*

Chain link model (in other studies called interactive or network model), shows that science research impacts innovation activity indirectly through accumulated knowledge factor, which is delivered to the innovation process participants in a form of the information.

The model conceptualizes innovation in terms of interaction between market opportunities and firm's knowledge base capabilities. Each broad function involves a number of sub-processes, and their outcomes are highly uncertain. Accordingly there is no simple progression, it is often necessary to go back to earlier stages in order to overcome difficulties in development. This means feedback between all parts of the process. A key element in determining the success (or failure) of an innovation project is the extent to which firms manage to maintain effective links between phases of the innovation process: the model emphasizes, for instance, the central importance of continuous interaction between marketing and invention / design stages.¹⁴

Multi dimensional perception of the innovation processes means, that current models take into the account so called network effects manifested through collaborations and spillovers, which impact the economic analysis in the conceptual way.

¹⁴ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

The deployment of the network mechanisms in the economy are partly dependent on the development of *global information networks* on which what Manuel Castells refers to as the *network society*.¹⁵

The driving forces behind economic growth and development in a networked economy are not natural resources or physical goods but the information viewed as providing the foundation for the transformation of existing social and economic relationships.¹⁶

Certain parts of the “new” (network) economy may benefit from increasing returns to scale, network effects and externalities. The value of communications networks and Internet applications, for instance, increases as more participants are concerned. This situation entails considerable spillovers, and these contribute to higher Total Factor Production growth and further growth.¹⁷

According to *Metcalf's law* the value of a network is the square of its size. Therefore a network that doubles in size will be four times as valuable because there are four times as many exchanges that can occur due to the larger number of interconnections.

The knowledge accumulation is the second important feature of the innovation network model. Innovate companies can participate in the knowledge exchange by spillover effect due to the fact that knowledge is:

- cumulative asset
- non- rival and partially exclusive one (in absence of protection through patent or other protecting mechanisms)¹⁸

These features can be best visualized by the spillover effect. The spillover effect was included in the endogenous growth model analysis by P. Romer¹⁹ who expanded R. Solow²⁰ neoclassic model of growth. In his growth model P. Romer showed that, as knowledge is non-rival resource, it may be used by several economic groups at the same time and at nil cost.

¹⁵ Castells M. (1998), *The Information age: Economy, Society and Culture*, Vol. 1,2,3,: The Network Society, Oxford: Blackwell

¹⁶ OECD (1997), *Global Information Infrastructure –Global Information Society Policy Requirements*, Committee for Information, Computers and Communication Policy, OECD Publications, Paris

¹⁷ OECD (2000), *New Economy? Changing Role of Innovation and Information Technology in Growth*, OECD Publications, Paris

¹⁸ ERASME laboratory (2004), *A 3 % R&D effort in Europe in 2010: an analysis of the consequences, using the Nemesis model*

¹⁹ Romer P. M. (1986), *Increasing returns and long-run growth*, *Journal of Political Economy*, 94

Knowledge can also be utilised as an exclusive asset by other innovation process participants, stimulating inventions and internal research.

Jones and Williams²¹ and Cameron²² identified four types of spillovers operating within the economy:

- Technological spillovers due to the circulation of knowledge, patenting or movement of the labour force: these spillovers may be between companies, between sectors or international. One interesting example in that group is the open source model.
- Surplus transfers: even in the absence of spillovers, the innovator cannot hold on to all the company gains engendered by an innovation, especially because of the price reductions that it may lead to. The size of the appropriation of the gains depends on the structure of the market
- The third spillover is a negative one: it is the result of Schumpeter's creative destruction process: new ideas accelerate the displacement of former production processes, which leads to losses.
- The congestive effects linked to the interrelation between innovations: if innovations can be *substituted*, this spillover is negative as it leads to a duplication of R&D effort. In this case, one could achieve the same research result with less R&D and a broader distribution of the innovation. However, if innovations *complement* each other, the spillover is positive as each innovation increases the profitability of the others.

Innovation produces effects in the company, but the distribution of the innovation via a range of channels (patents, scientific literature, exchanges of expertise, employee exchanges and exchanges of assets between firms or nations) will produce further, highly significant effects that will increase the returns on research to the point that they may become non-decreasing.²³

²⁰ Solow, R. (1956), A Contribution to the Theory of Economic Growth, Quarterly Journal of Economics 70

²¹ Jones C.I. and C. Williams (1998), Measuring the social return to R&D, Quarterly Journal of Economics, November; after: ERASME laboratory (2004), A 3 % R&D effort in Europe in 2010: an analysis of the consequences, using the Nemesis model

²² Cameron G. (1998), Innovation and Growth: a survey of the empirical evidence, mimeo; after: ERASME laboratory (2004), A 3 % R&D effort in Europe in 2010: an analysis of the consequences, using the Nemesis model

²³ ERASME laboratory (2004), A 3 % R&D effort in Europe in 2010: an analysis of the consequences, using the Nemesis model

3. Innovation and network mechanisms (innovation object oriented analysis)

The innovation creation, diffusion and adaptation mechanisms involve spillovers, which are manifested through networks of exchange. Where as knowledge it self and its accumulation can be perceived as a subject feature of the innovation analysis, the network mechanism is an object in the analysis (it represents actors and the topology of knowledge exchange).

Innovation collaboration (network mechanisms) involves particular type of asset exchange – knowledge which has intangible nature. Here the “knowledge exchange” or “knowledge” itself is associated with the innovation object oriented analysis.

Development and use of knowledge in innovation processes is essentially a collaborative activity, and it is based on:

- creation of new knowledge through formal or informal variation or recombination;
- testing of knowledge through debate, scholarship, and market testing; and
- passing on knowledge through teaching, imitation, and publication.²⁴

With the increased production of information and knowledge²⁵ (knowledge economy regards an information as a forth important production asset next to: land, capital, and labour) the sources of knowledge tend to be widely dispersed. In economy there are mechanisms emerging to organise distributed knowledge. They are usually created as interorganizational collaborations, which can take a number of forms (including research consortia, joint ventures, strategic alliances and subcontracting) and span wide range of key functions.

On the virtual network level (eg. Internet) the Open Source movement is an example of the knowledge facilitation trend.²⁶ On the project level, the Open Source software movement is the most distinctive one but there are also other that concern citation creation as well as research and development in the various science fields (eg. distributed computing projects).

²⁴ Wagner C., Cave J., Tesch T., Allee V., Thomson R., Leydesdorff L., Botterman M. (2005), ERAnets Evaluation of Networks of Collaboration among participants in IST Research and their evolution to Collaborations in the European Research Area

²⁵ Knowledge is distinct from simple information. Knowledge is information which is processed and utilized for a certain purpose or use.

²⁶ Powell W. F, Grodal S. (2004), The Oxford Handbook of Innovation, Chapter 3: Networks of Innovators, Oxford University Press, Oxford, New York

Innovation is increasingly tied to the ability of companies to connect across virtual links, to find new markets, to access the latest technology breakthroughs and to quickly configure working partnerships to bring products and services to market. Networks of collaboration are seen as one strategy to meet these key challenges.

The reason for the increased network collaboration is purely economic and derives from the economy of scale paradigm i.e. the productivity of collective invention. The recombination of ideas in collaborative teams adds to the speed and relevance of innovation.²⁷ Project that uses more knowledge sources will be always more productive than the project using only one source.

In socio economic terms a network can be described as: a group of actors connected by some event or affiliation. In this study, networks include research organisations linked by participation in common projects, and also research organisations connected by co-authorship; or corporations connected by a joint research venture.²⁸

Networks can be differentiated with respect to their duration and stability, as well as whether they forged to accomplish a specific task or evolve out of pre-existing bonds of association. Networks vary from short-term projects to long-term relationships, hierarchical and heterarchical, with distributed authority and self-organising features.²⁹

In economics, networks can have similar properties but more properly they can be divided, in accordance with the logical criterion, into vertical and horizontal networks according to the value-adding chain. Vertical networks connect firms or production activities along a particular value-adding chain or production process; whereas horizontal networks connect individuals and organizations in particular functional areas (such as research, production, logistics, marketing, etc.)³⁰

There is also presumption that network systems (such as internet) can self organise themselves in a functional way. This phenomenon is characterized as the "loose coupling":

²⁷ Wagner C., et al. (2005), ERAnets Evaluation of Networks of Collaboration among participants in IST Research and their evolution to Collaborations in the European Research Area

²⁸ *ibid.*

²⁹ *ibid.*

³⁰ Porter, M. (1985), *Competitive Advantage*, New York: Free Press; after: Hämläinen T., Schienstock G. (2000), *Innovation Networks and Network Policies*

various independent actors develop relatively loose relationships among each other to pursue some common goals.³¹

European Commission Framework Programmes (especially FP6) have worked as an instrument in building networks. The figure below shows Specific Target Research Projects cooperation network (STREPs)³² for the FP6 call 1, which are suited for smaller consortia and more narrowly focused research (dedicated to specific innovation). The instruments as a project structure are likely to involve a innovation in the strict sense, but also more likely to be self contained – star shaped topology³³ (Figure 4).

³¹ Johannison, B. (1987): Beyond Process and Structure: Social Exchange Networks. International Studies of Management and Organisation; after: Hämäläinen T., Schienstock G. (2000), Innovation Networks and Network Policies

³² European Commission uses 3 types of instruments to favour research teams in the FP6 (<http://www.cordis.lu/fp6/instruments.htm>):

- aimed at generating, demonstrating and validating new knowledge through research and development, and is composed of Integrated Projects (IPs) and Specific Targeted Research Projects (STREPs);
- Networks of Excellence (NoEs), an instrument aimed at the durable integration of the participants' activities/capacities;
- aimed at supporting collaboration and coordination, and other activities (such as conferences and studies) and is composed of Coordination Actions (CAs) and Specific Support Actions (SSAs).

³³ Wagner C. et al. (2005), ERAnets Evaluation of Networks of Collaboration among participants in IST Research and their evolution to Collaborations in the European Research Area

Figure 4
FP6 STREPs* network topology

Source: Wagner C. (2005), Applying Network Analysis to Research Evaluation: The ERAnets Project
* STREPs, call 1 retained, projects as stars, component 1, diameter 15, average path length 5.6 (colour is number of steps away from the centre, from 1-5)

The structure of the network – its topology, seems to be so important because it visualizes potential innovation creation and diffusion processes. In the knowledge based theory of the firm apart from *social capital* and *availability of complementary assets*, the innovation process depends on the *diversity of knowledge* and *intensity of communication*³⁴, which are organisational factors embedded in general properties of the network.

New knowledge is typically created when different types of knowledge is exchanged and combined or when the same knowledge elements are combined in a new way.

This stands in accordance with the Schumpeterian approach which states that, diverse production process involves *producing different goods or producing same goods (also intangible) thanks to the different production method i.e. combination of resources*.³⁵

³⁴ Hämäläinen T., Schienstock G. (2000), Innovation Networks and Network Policies, <http://www.oecd.org/dataoecd/35/8/2100869.pdf>

³⁵ Schumpeter, J. (1934), *The Theory of Economic Development*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

Today, individual knowledge bases tend to be so specialised that the required diversity of knowledge for major innovations can only be reached when two or more experts combine their different specialised knowledge sets and create a partially shared knowledge base.

Different knowledge sets of individuals cannot be combined and shared very easily. The combination requires the development of shared language, overlapping knowledge structures, and common cognitive frames together with a meta-level recognition of each other's knowledge domains. This involves highly tacit types of knowledge, which are very difficult to communicate. However, once established, the shared knowledge base permits individuals to exchange and combine aspects of knowledge which are not common between them.³⁶ This provides new insights, perspectives and meanings, which would not otherwise emerge

On the other hand, when the knowledge sets are very similar both communication and the creation of shared knowledge are very easy. However, the low diversity of knowledge does not encourage learning and invention.

Network relationships usually take a relatively long period of time to develop but, once established, they tend to be characterized by mutual interdependence, intensive communication, reciprocity, and high levels of trust, which can be especially distinctive for the Open Source model.

4. Open Source and innovation model

The Open Source is an interesting example of innovation model in the ICT sector. It introduces no-linear cooperation process between the project parties. Although model is mainly used for the software engineering and development, it can also be perceived as a general theoretical model for the innovation development in other fields.

One of the first open source model analysis was done by Eric Raymond.³⁷ In his work Raymond compared the linear model of software development, mostly in big, concern companies to the middle age cathedral and open source model to the free knowledge exchange bazaar. The cathedral style leaves not much flexibility at the project development

³⁶ Grant, R. (1996), Toward a Knowledge-based Theory of the Firm, Strategic Management, Journal, Special Issue, December; after: Hämmäläinen T., Schienstock G. (2000), Innovation Networks and Network Policies

³⁷ Raymond Eric S, (1997), The Cathedral and the Bazaar, <http://www.catb.org/~esr/writings/cathedral-bazaar/cathedral-bazaar/>

level, keeping processes stages internal: *Invention, production, analytical design to marketing distribution*. In that model the accent is put on the control of the development work, clear hierarchy, strict definition of the functions for each developer, clear organization of work and defined management structure. The model defines *a priori* what, who and in what time delivers project results and further more, what is the range of deliverables of work.

Raymond applies bazaar characteristics to the open source model, where all parties in the network are involved in the process at the equal level (there is no hierarchical structure of work). The bazaar development style gives more flexibility depending on knowledge exchange in developed network mechanisms.

Open source tend to be created upon the *star network topology*. One party in the network is distinctive, but put on the same level as to implementing changes in the project, and plays the role of the hub – which organizes and coordinates work. In that case the efficiency of the work consolidation depends on the hub (it can be an organization but most likely the individual). Figure 5 shows example of Open Source project topology.

Figure 5
Open Source Project Topology example
CIA, a system for tracking open source projects in real-time

Source: CIA, a system for tracking open source projects in real-time, <http://www.advogato.org/person/micahjd/>

Raymond also defines preconditions for successful bazaar-style development, which include both the qualifications of the project leader and the state of work (software code in ICT projects) at the time one goes public and starts to try to build a co-developer community. He states: “*It’s fairly clear that one cannot code from the ground up in bazaar style. One can test, debug and improve in bazaar style, but it would be very hard to originate a project in bazaar mode.*”³⁸

It means that open source innovation development model if applied to any sector would concern (like ICT project) the two development phases: *Detailed design and test* and *Redesign and produce* (see chain-chain link model: Chapter 1 Figure 2), and depend on already existing network relations.

The simplicity of its advantages can be expressed by the phrase said by Linus Torvalds (Linux project author): “given enough eyeballs, all bugs are shallow”. This implies that hence the chain-link (network , interactive) model’s redesigning and production phase (in software engineering: debugging phase - where software errors are removed, either through code inspection or software testing) can be parallelized, given some coordination between developers.

The efficiency of such process increases as the number of the parties in the network increases. According to *Metcalf’s law*³⁹ the value of a network is approximately the square of its size (N^2). Therefore a network that doubles in size will be four times as valuable because there are four times as many exchanges that can occur due to the larger number of interconnections. Since a network user cannot connect to itself, the actual calculation is:

$$N(N-1), \text{ or } N^2 - N.$$

The open source model tends to concern smaller project, done by individuals of SMEs specializing in open source project. The majority of open source developers are professional programmers hired by the companies on the regular basis. The important characteristic of the model (in ICT sector) is often release information in the upgrades of the project (hence the phrase: code often release often) and changed (upgraded) product itself.

³⁸ *ibid.*

³⁹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Metcalf%27s_law

Going into details, the bazaar-like model in ICT sector, works in some sense as an accretion model, where a working application with a reasonable level of usefulness gets more and more functionality and changes, and in this way it gets incrementally better. Due to this incremental development, there is a window of time in the initial phases of development, when the project deliverable (software) is still not functional enough to attract attention from other developers (programmers), when some kind of funding would be very convenient (in terms of money, time or other resources) to reach an initial point of usability. After this point is reached, the accretion process can start and show its power.⁴⁰

Figure below shows comparison of the project results between linear (classic, proprietary: cathedral) and open source (bazaar, network) model.

Figure 6
Incremental changes in the Open Source Model

It is uncertain whether the open source model could be applied to innovation development process in every sector. It is clear though, that this model due to its characteristic concerns knowledge sharing and intangible asset sharing at the last stages of the innovation creation process. The Figure below show the chain link innovation model with the last two stages perceived as the open source exchange network and no commercial phase-last phase (Figure 7).

⁴⁰ Working group on Libre Software, (2000), Free Software / Open Source: Information Society Opportunities for Europe?, DG INFSO

Figure 7
Chain-link model for the Open Source innovation

Source: Modification of the Chain-link Model (Kline S. J., Rosenberg N., (1986), An Overview of Innovation)

Another constraint for applying the model to economic innovation definition is in some cases the lack of commercial stimulation. The deliverables of the innovation project are free (zero costs guaranteed by the product license) for every interested party. The motivation factor in terms of potential benefits (financial) is not so strong as in the non-open source project, or is indirect. The open source projects usually originate in different motivation, than financial direct financial profit. Eric Raymond in *The Cathedral and the Bazaar*, writing about Linux open source project states that: *“The ‘utility function’ Linux hackers are maximizing is not classically economic, but is the intangible of their own ego satisfaction and reputation among other hackers. (One may call their motivation ‘altruistic’, but this ignores the fact that altruism is itself a form of ego satisfaction for the altruist)”*

This paradoxically stands in contradiction with the Schumpeterian innovation theory, which states that innovation process must be closed with the successful commercialization. The remuneration here though, can be perceived in terms of knowledge gains or direct financial profit from service supported to the product.

In summary, following characteristics can be applied to the open source innovation development model:

- non linear (network based)
- marginal (incrementally added value)

- microeconomic scale impact –project level, mostly small organizations or individual involved (not big corporations)
- outputs are free: zero costs guaranteed by license – commercial constraints

5. Measuring innovation – classical indicators

There are three broad areas of classical innovation indicator use in Science, Technology and Innovation analysis:

- R&D data
- Data on patent applications grants and citations
- Bibliometric data (data on scientific publications and citations)

Generally the data can be collected at the macro and micro economic level, measuring inputs (eg. Including innovation state aid, business investments) or outputs, which can be more difficult to measure in the case of no technological change (organizational and managerial if there is no direct link between them nor economic output involved).

R&D is still the most important innovation input. In all sectors investment in capital equipment related to the new product introduction is the major component of innovation expenditure. There are several basic ways of describing R&D based innovation performance, depending on the level of the analysis. On the microeconomic level it can be R&D/ Sales ratio. For a industry (sector level) this is usually ratio of business expenditure on R&D (BERD) to total production or value added. On the national economy level the indicator is constructed by showing the ratio of gross expenditure on R&D to GDP (GERD).⁴¹

Measuring R&D alone is not sufficient for the capturing whole impact of innovation on business macro and/ or micro performance (as it also depend on learning, knowledge creation and on technological factors).

⁴¹ Keith Smith (2004), The Oxford Handbook of Innovation, Chapter 6: Measuring Innovation, Oxford University Press, Oxford, New York

The group of classical indicators which are knowledge measurement based are **patent indicators**. The patent indicator is recognized as OECD in the Science Technology and Industry Scoreboard initiative as a main measurement of innovation.⁴²

According to the document for R&D and innovation related measurements and statistics, the OECD's Frascati Manual,⁴³ patent is an intellectual property right relating to inventions in the technical field. Patent based indicators (eg. patent count or family patent count) provide a measure of the output of country's innovative activity: its inventions. Patent data are also used to identify changes in the structure and evolution of inventive activity in countries, industries, companies and technologies by mapping changes in technology dependency, diffusion and penetration.

The advantages of the patent based innovation indicators are seen in their systematic, old history and hard data records. The patent system systematically collects information concerning inventive technologies with commercial promise relating inventions to the relevant technologies, and also providing links to relevant technical and scientific literature.⁴⁴

Patent indicators have their weaknesses, which derives from the nature of the patent system and patent itself- they mark the emergence of a new invention and not a commercial innovation. The Frascati Manual points out that, patent indicators miss the innovations which were not patented due to copyrights or trade secrecy. The patent system also varies within the countries and in some cases the comparison is difficult to make.

Another classical innovation indicator is **bibliometrics**. The bibliometrics is the generic term for data on publications. Originally it was limited to collecting data on numbers of scientific articles and other publications, classified by author and/ or by institution, field of science, country etc. in order to construct simple "productivity" indicators for academic research. Subsequently, more sophisticated and multidimensional techniques based on citations in articles (and also patents) were developed. The resulting citation indexes and co-citation

⁴² OECD (2003), Science, Technology and Industry Scoreboard, OECD Publications, Paris

⁴³ OECD (2002), Proposed Standard Practise for Surveys on Research and Experimental Development, Frascati Manual, OECD Publications, Paris

⁴⁴ Keith Smith (2004), The Oxford Handbook of Innovation, Chapter 6: Measuring Innovation, Oxford University Press, Oxford, New York

analyses are used both to obtain more sensitive measures of research quality and to trace the development of fields of science and networks.⁴⁵

The bibliometric analysis uses data on numbers and authors of scientific publications and on articles and citations therein (as well as the citations in patents) to measure output of individual research teams, institutions and countries to identify national and international networks, and map the development of new (multidisciplinary) fields of science and technology.

6. Measuring innovation – new focus in the innovation indicators

Majority of classical measurements reflects the industrial era, depending on measuring products and tangible assets rather than knowledge and processes, which are characteristic for the knowledge economy.

The emergence of a knowledge-based economy is often associated with the growing share of R&D-intensive industries and with the increasing use of advanced knowledge in hitherto “low-technology” industries. This view is far too narrow. The production of goods and services is becoming more knowledge-intensive but not necessarily more R&D-intensive. Many rapidly growing new service activities (*e.g.* software, venture capital funds, etc.) employ highly qualified labour and are highly intensive in immaterial investment but not in formal R&D. They belong to the most innovative activities, are based on technical progress (especially in information technology), but do not appear among the “high-tech” sectors.⁴⁶

The 21st Century Innovation Working Group in the National Innovation Initiative Final Report⁴⁷ shows development of innovation of the innovation indicator in the four metrics generation groups (Figure 8):

- the **first generation** of metrics reflected a linear concept of innovation focusing on inputs such as R&D investment, education expenditure, capital expenditure, research personnel, university graduates, technological intensity etc.

⁴⁵ OECD (2002), Proposed Standard Practise for Surveys on Research and Experimental Development, Frascati Manual, OECD Publications, Paris

⁴⁶ OECD (1999), Managing National Innovation Systems, OECD Publications, Paris

⁴⁷ 21st Century Innovation Working Group (2004), Working Group Final Report, Council of Competitiveness in the National Innovation Initiative, Washington DC

- the **second generation** complemented input indicators by accounting for the intermediate outputs of S&T activities. Typical examples include patent counts, scientific publications, counts of new products and processes, high-trade.
- the **third generation** is focused on a richer set of innovation indicators and indexes based on surveys and integration of publicly available data. The primary focus is on benchmarking and rank ordering a nation’s capacity to innovate. A main difficulty at the moment is the validity of international data comparisons and incorporating service sector innovations (where the process is the product) into the surveys.

Figure 8
Evolution of Innovation Metrics by Generation (examples)

First generation INPUT INDICATORS (1950-60)	Second generation OUTPUT INDICATORS (1970-80)	Third generation INNOVATION INDICATORS (1990)	Fourth Generation PROCESS INDICATORS (2000 – present)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R&D expenditures - S&T Personnel - Capital - Technical intensity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patents - Publications - Products - Quality change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovation surveys - Indexing - Benchmarking innovation capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge - Intangibles - Networks - Demand - Clusters management techniques - Risk/Return - System dynamics

Source: 21st Century Innovation Working Group (2004), Working Group Final Report, Council of Competitiveness in the National Innovation Initiative

- Relevant **fourth generation** metrics currently at an development stage include:
 - **Knowledge indicators.** Here the scope is put on knowledge that underlies creation of tangible assets and the ways it developed and diffused.
 - **Networks.** Innovation processes multitude of network mechanisms. Measurement of the collaborations between innovating organizations aims in understanding innovation creation and diffusion.
 - **Conditions for innovation.** This group of indicators provide measures for the innovation environment (i.e. Economic demand, public policy environment, infrastructure, social attitudes and cultural factors), in which organizations form and match expectations and capabilities to innovation.

The work of Rosenberg⁴⁸ and of Rosenberg and Kline⁴⁹ on the innovation indicator development has brought two main implications to the theory. The first is that novelty implies not just the creation of completely new products or processes, but relatively small scale changes in product performance which may – over a long period – have major technological and economic implications. The second is the importance of non-R&D inputs to innovation - design activities, engineering developments and experimentation, training, exploration of markets for new products, etc.⁵⁰

Despite the existence of standard methods and classical indicators, measuring innovation seems to be a complex problem. Majority of tasks in the innovation creation process depend not only on research or tangible inventions but also on knowledge creation and learning which have more intangible character and are difficult to capture.

Modern innovation theories rest on “resource-based” (subject oriented) theory of the firm, in which firms create physical and intangible assets that underpin capabilities. Innovative learning can be seen as change in the knowledge bases on which the capabilities rest, but unfortunately neither of it can be measured in the direct way. However just as “research” can be captured via expenditures on certain activities or by the use of time by the certain research personnel, so learning process can to some extent be captured by activities such as design, training, market research, tooling up, etc.

The Innovation Score Board prepared by the European Commission, DG Enterprise⁵¹ introduces indicators that involve knowledge based and network related activity measurements.

This work stresses the significance of innovation diversity: *“Firms can innovate through product, process, organisational or marketing innovation, by adopting new technology developed by other firms, or through intensive in-house research activities. In each case, the capabilities required by the firm to innovate are very different. Consequently, simple aggregate indicators of the*

⁴⁸ Rosenberg N. (1976), Perspectives on Technology, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

⁴⁹ Kline S. and Rosenberg N. (1986), An Overview of Innovation, in: R. Landu (ed.), The Positive Sum Strategy: Harnessing Technology For Economic Growth, Washington: National Academy Press

⁵⁰ Keith Smith (2004), The Oxford Handbook of Innovation, Chapter 6: Measuring Innovation, Oxford University Press, Oxford, New York

⁵¹ Arundel A. and Hollanders H. (2005), EXIS: Explanatory Approach to Innovation Scoreboards, MERIT, European Commission, DG Enterprise

percentage of 'innovative' firms in a particular country provide very little information of value to policy.”

Most of the indicators included in the scoreboard have macroeconomic character – they are focusing on firm level innovation diversity. These are two sets of indicators: *human resources; creation of new knowledge, transmission; application of knowledge; and innovation finance, output and markets.*⁵²

Meaningful for the innovation network process is the knowledge flow indicator. The composite indicator measures the uptake by firms of knowledge from external sources – it is essentially an indicator of the diffusion of knowledge, rather than its production within the firm. Good performance of the indicator is based on the high rate of international collaboration, a high value attached to information from the higher education sector and to all external knowledge sources, and high level of openness to tangible knowledge.⁵³

To capture the value diffusion path of technology i.e. register the international flow of industrial property and know how in terms of innovation the Technology and Balance of payment indicator (TBP), was developed.

The OECD uses this type of innovation proxy indicator based on data originally collected to measure the international diffusion of disembodied technology by reporting all intangible transactions relating to trade in technical knowledge and in services with technology content between partners in different countries.

The following operations are included in the TBP: patents (purchases, sales); licences for patents; know-how (not patented); models and designs; trademarks (including franchising); technical services; finance of industrial R&D outside national territory.⁵⁴

Appendix III⁵⁵ shows summary of the strengths and weaknesses of some science and technology indicators, representative for the innovation.

⁵² Trend Chart, Innovation Policy in Europe,
<http://trendchart.cordis.lu/scoreboards/scoreboard2004/indicators.cfm>

⁵³ Arundel A and Hollanders H. (2005), EXIS: Explanatory Approach to Innovation Scoreboards, MERIT, European Commission, DG Enterprise

7. Economic impact of the innovation – ICT example

It is proved by modern economy theories that innovation highly contributes to the economic growth through the improvement of productivity of production factors (capital and/ or labour) and change in price and structure of the competitiveness. Productivity is the key in increasing real income and competitiveness and is one of the most important tools of industrial performance.

Modern (new) growth theories were developed in the 1960's, and followed on from the work of Solow and Swan neoclassical growth model, which was published in 1956. Their models showed that the long-term economic growth rate is determined by the intensity of technical progress and an increase in the working population, both of which are exogenous.

The new growth models, endogenous growth models integrate private investment into physical capital, technological innovation, human capital or public capital as sources of technical progress. Unlike traditional models, in which returns to scale are decreasing,⁵⁶ the new growth models assume increasing returns. These are due to the explicit inclusion of the role of knowledge, which accumulates over time. Knowledge comes from invention, which comes from research. The result is innovation, as long as the market and the company's means permit it. This permeates into the economy and leads to further innovation. The stock of knowledge is increased still further.

Systems for protecting innovation, such as patents or secrecy, only serve to postpone this increase in the stock of knowledge, from which all companies benefit. This is why the economy benefits from positive spillovers at the start of increasing returns to scale.⁵⁷ Thanks to this property of the economy, economic policies have rediscovered their influence on economic growth.⁵⁸

⁵⁴ OECD (2002), Proposed Standard Practise for Surveys on Research and Experimental Development, Frascati Manual, OECD Publications, Paris

⁵⁵ Calvert, J et. al (1996), Innovation Outputs in European Industry: Analysis from CIS, Brighton: Science Policy Research Unit

⁵⁶ In exogenous growth models, the marginal productivity of physical capital decreases with time, which generates a decrease in returns of scale.

⁵⁷ Spillovers are engendered by investment in physical capital in the 1986 Romer model; they stem directly from the sector of research into equipment assets in the 1990 model, and from the innovation of quality in the 1997 Aghion and Howitt model.

⁵⁸ ERASME laboratory (2004), A 3 % R&D effort in Europe in 2010: an analysis of the consequences, using the Nemesis model

Innovation contribution in economic growth can be best shown on the example of the information and communication technologies (ICT) and their impact on total factor productivity.

The development of ICT in the United States and its impact on growth and productivity gains illustrates the links that can occur between innovation, productivity and growth, as long as the conditions of this circle (especially the reorganisation of work) are all combined. These links are at the heart of growth theories and, increasingly, of applied models.

ICT can contribute to labor productivity growth through both capital deepening and total factor productivity (TFP) growth (or multi factor productivity).

Capital deepening refers to the change in labor productivity attributable to higher levels of capital per worker. TFP growth refers to improvements in the efficiency with which capital and labor are combined to produce output.

Under standard assumptions, labor productivity growth (the change in output per unit of labor input) can be expressed as:

$$\left(\frac{\hat{Y}}{\hat{L}}\right) = \alpha \left(\frac{\hat{K}}{\hat{L}}\right) + \hat{A}$$

where Y is output, L is labor, K is capital, α is the share of capital in national income, A is the level of total factor productivity, and $\hat{}$ denotes a percentage change. To measure the gain arising from smarter production, output has to be compared with the combined inputs of labour and capital. This is what is referred to as total factor productivity.⁵⁹

To structure the analysis of economic growth and its causes, OECD⁶⁰ established an analysis framework (Figure 9), which consists of three major features:

- **First** it explores some of “proximate” sources of growth. These relate to the familiar factors of production, labour and capital, and to their productivity. All changes in an economy’s production can be attributed to changes in the quantity of labour or capital

⁵⁹ OECD (2000), *Is There a New Economy? First Report on the OECD Growth Project*, OECD Publications, Paris

⁶⁰ OECD (2000), *New Economy? Changing Role of Innovation and Information Technology in Growth*, OECD Publications, Paris

employed, to changes in the quality of these inputs or to advances in technology and efficiency (the productivity component).

- **Second**, the central part of Figure 9 evokes some underlying (“ultimate”) determinants of growth. Many potential determinants which include investment in fixed capital, human capital and innovation, the degree of an economy’s interaction and openness, the strength of the diffusion process, mobility of human resources and cost factors.
- **Third**, the right-hand part of Figure 9 is closely linked to the central part and concerns the impact of policy and institutional factors on these determinants of growth. It addresses the role of macroeconomic policy, product, financial and labour market policies, regulatory reform, technology and innovation policy, etc.

Figure 9
Analytical framework of growth factors in economy

Source: OECD (2000), *New Economy? Changing Role of Innovation and Information Technology in Growth*, OECD Publications, Paris

The existing analysis has established that ICT is contributing to labor productivity growth through both increases in the levels of ICT capital per worker (“ICT-related capital deepening”) and TFP growth in ICT production, though the precise magnitudes of these contributions remain a subject of debate. The main outstanding issue is whether ICT has contributed to TFP growth more generally by increasing the efficiency of production, either through usage or knowledge spillovers from the production of ICT goods.

In summary, OECD⁶¹ distinguishes three main channels can be identified through which ICT can affect potential growth rates:

- an acceleration of productivity in the ICT-producing sectors themselves, and a growing size of ICT-producing sectors in the economy;
- capital deepening across the economy, driven by rapid investment in ICT equipment, and resulting in a boost to labour productivity; and
- widespread spillover effects on productivity arising from IC technology.

Special attention in the researches is given to developments in labour productivity, allowing for human capital accumulation and multi-factor productivity, allowing for changes in the composition and quality of physical capital. Countries that have managed to improve their growth performance share some common elements: improvements in labour utilisation; a generalised enhancement of human capital; and a rapid adoption of the new information and communication technology by many industries.⁶²

8. Conclusions – innovation policy

Nowadays interest in innovation has increased. As economic means such as cost-cut economy and quality-economy are brought to the *canon* of economic science and practise innovation creates similar vision to the *Holly Grail* in the quest for the sources of additional economy development boost.

With defining the innovation, it can be measured and practically utilized. The innovation in its economic understanding is still interpreted differently, but this difference is not of a substantial nature (Appendix IV). There is a significant work done for innovation definition harmonisation as well as well as extending the reach over its already defined factors (involvement of knowledge factor, network mechanisms in the innovation creation and diffusion processes).

The rise of endogenous growth models brought the presumption that role of the innovation in economy is more understood and now it is a time to reach for the economic development

⁶¹ OECD (2003), *The Sources of Growth in OECD Countries*, OECD Publications, Paris

policies and tools that could develop sustainable model for the innovation stimulation. The interest of policy makers in innovation therefore is of the high issue.

Changing role of innovation theory is visualized in Appendix V. The time line is divided into two parts: Industrial and Information Revolution era as the important sources of the economic changes, stimulating innovation phenomenon. Innovation concept focus has been changing over time: firstly it included only on the invention aspects, later the innovation conceptualization, which led to innovation direct policies.

Modern (new) growth theories, rapid expansion of the network technologies, (such as the Internet, which is in a way the most effective ICT) brought the focus to the possibility of enhancing economic performance through the innovation based policy decision making process.

At the economic development policy level, two general approaches in the policy implementation can be distinguished.

First general trend indicates that policy regulations are the consequence of market mechanisms, already existing at the certain level of market niche (in regards to newly emerging innovative sectors). This standpoint is called bottom up because the regulatory framework tends to touch only basic level and the micro scale of already existing economic processes. The example of such phenomenon is Silicon Valley in CA, USA. The innovative environment of the Silicon Valley rose from the smart work force, the university environment and entrepreneurship concentration (knowledge and specialized skills), which adopted the and implemented technological results. The regulatory policy in that case was minimal.

Second policy trend is called top down approach, which means that authorities through the policy making process, stimulate the economic environment to achieve certain effects. Information Society policy is an example of top down policy stimulating development and deployment of innovations especially in the ICT field. There exist whole set of economic development tools, which can be used to implement certain type of economic policy. The examples here are initiatives created by Japan and EU innovation policy. Sixth Framework

⁶² *ibid.*

Programme IST (designed and implemented at the central level) is an example of a science base and private sector economic potential stimulation and infrastructure development tool. Its aim is to generate innovation added value projects with a certain spillover effects.

The most distinctive problem of the economic policy and especially in the innovation field is that it is not always market oriented in the Keynesian understanding. Overregulated interventionist policies can cause even greater failures in the market and economic turndown.

There have been several studies in terms of findings caused by deregulation, liberalization, as well higher knowledge accumulation in the economy.

The European Commission has carried out a number of policy simulations of the gains from the implementation of measures included in the Lisbon strategy. Interestingly this analysis shows that deregulation alone (i.e. bringing the level of EU product market regulation down to the US level) would not be enough to fill the gap with the US in terms of per capita GDP. To reach this target Europe would have to increase spending in R&D, education, and ICT.⁶³

The innovation policy therefore should be a market-oriented (eg. in terms of possibility of invention commercialization opportunities) in order to be successfully implemented and most preferably liberal dimension (eg. simplification of the tax system and for the innovative entrepreneurship). Nobel prize winner economist, Friedrich A. Hayek (1899 -1992) stated that: “*government ultimately can't fix economic problems, it can only hope to convince people to fix them for themselves*”. For the policymaking process it does not mean that the government should not take any actions at all, it means that free market oriented policy is crucial for the consideration as a representative of the human rationale, as the most important market factor (i.e. entrepreneurship creation: eg. liberal SMEs policy).

According to the OECD⁶⁴ governments need to play an integrating role in managing knowledge on an economy-wide basis by making technology and innovation policy an integral part of overall economic policy. This requires co-ordinated contributions from a variety of policies in order to:

⁶³ European Commission (2003), The EU Economy 2003 Review, after: Guerrieri P., Maggi B., Meliciani V., Padoan P. C. (2005), Technology diffusion, services, and endogenous growth in Europe. Is the Lisbon Strategy useful?, University of Rome

- Secure framework conditions that are conducive to innovation, such as a stable macroeconomic environment, a supportive tax and regulatory environment, and appropriate infrastructure and education and training policies.
- Remove more specific barriers to innovation in the business sector and increase synergies between public and private investment in innovation.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development and European Commission are two intergovernmental organisations, which put a strong focus its economic policy on the innovation aspects (OECD – science and innovation policy, EC – redefining The Lisbon strategy).

There have been several innovation initiatives done by OECD and EC, which purpose was to define innovation policy and create clear innovation measurements on the macro and microeconomic level. The EC initiatives are mostly of a regulatory character. Through the Lisbon agenda EC sees an importance for stimulating R&D, using Barcelona criterion of reaching 3% GDP for research and development expenditures in each member state.

Redefining Lisbon agenda policy sees a great necessity for investment in research and innovation to generate growth and jobs.

In 2005 the European Commission launched two major proposals to strengthen Europe's position in ICTs; the Seventh Research Framework Programme (FP7) and the Competitiveness and Innovation Programme (CIP).⁶⁵ In its proposal for FP7, the Commission asks for a substantial increase in ICT research budget. The increase will contribute to closing the ICT gap with other leading economies if it is fully complemented by increases in private and public research spending. The Commission sees FP7 primarily as a lever of overall R&D investment.⁶⁶

⁶⁴ OECD (1999), *Managing National Innovation Systems*, OECD Publications, Paris

⁶⁵ FP7 proposes to attribute 1800BN EUR annually to ICTs. The ICT Policy Support Specific Programme of the CIP proposes 800M EUR for 2007 to 2013 to encourage take-up and use of ICTs.

⁶⁶ SEC (2005), *The Lisbon Strategy emphasises investment in research and innovation to generate growth and jobs*

Besides one integrated innovation policy there exist various member state policies, which must stay in accordance with European Union regulations.

The US policy in that issue is conducted mostly at the state and regional level. The innovation policy is of very liberal nature, which accounts for stimulations of science and technology sector as well as research and development stimulation and infrastructure development (state investments). This is conducted most preferably by the demand side economic development tools (technology incubators, venture capital funds, research aid grants) rather than tax regulations, which create impact in the long term on budget.⁶⁷

Recent National Innovation Initiative is to develop coherent innovation policy, defining innovation and creating innovation system – an innovation development friendly environment consisting of private and public organizations and knowledge exchange channels.

The OECD puts the interest in the conceptualization sphere of the innovation in the economy. The recent important studies in that field include: innovation definition framework,⁶⁸ productivity analysis,⁶⁹ sources of economic growth,⁷⁰ technology and industry scoreboard,⁷¹ innovation measurement and indicator development.⁷²

Hence the endogenous (new) growth models, economic performance can be stimulated by other means than direct policy tools (e.g. direct investments, tax abatements and subsidies), which are of highly regulatory character and market failure dedicated.

Knowledge sharing through spillovers and network collaboration is even more strengthening innovation impacts, which generate synergies i.e. additional positive economic effects. With

⁶⁷ Example of such policy is Michigan SmartZones project, which consists of collaborations between universities, industry, research organizations, government, and other community institutions intended to stimulate the growth of technology-based businesses and jobs by aiding in the creation of recognized clusters of new and emerging businesses, those primarily focused on commercializing ideas, patents, and other opportunities surrounding corporate, university or private research institute R&D efforts; <http://medc.michigan.org/smartzones/>

⁶⁸ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

⁶⁹ OECD (2000), Is There a New Economy? First Report on the OECD Growth Project, OECD Publications, Paris

⁷⁰ OECD (2003), The Sources of Growth in OECD Countries, OECD Publications, Paris

⁷¹ OECD (2003), Science Technology and Industry Scoreboard, OECD Publications, Paris

⁷² OECD (2002), Proposed Standard Practise for Surveys on Research and Experimental Development, Frascati Manual, OECD Publications, Paris

the understanding of non linear nature of innovation new sets of measures, monitoring and evaluation tools are being developed.

An interesting example of the innovation network analysis is one conducted for the European Commission in the report on Evaluation of Networks of Collaboration in IST Research within European Research Area. The project developed and applied tools and methods to evaluate the networks of collaboration in IST within European Research Area, focusing on calls 1 and call 2 of Sixth Framework Programme.

Participants in the Sixth Framework Programme IST projects, when considered as project teams, create network know-how and conduct research. Networks –different institutions that join together for a time –limited, specific purpose – are increasingly recognized as an important tool for knowledge sharing and innovation. They are particularly important to the European Research Area (ERA) as a way to link geographically-distant centres of excellence and to disseminate knowledge across Europe. This vision of a networked knowledge economy is central to the Lisbon Objectives.⁷³ According to the report, through the IST Six Framework Programme European Commission succeeded in the creation stimulation and strengthening innovation network cooperation. (FP6 call 1 and call 2 comparison).

The 21'th Century Innovation Working Group⁷⁴ developed an interesting theoretical base in the field of new innovation indicators. In report prepared for the US government Department of Commerce (through the Council of Competitiveness), authors divide indicators into three general groups:

- **Knowledge indicators** include development and diffusion of knowledge that underlies creation of tangible asset and the ways it is developed and diffused.
- **Networks indicators** focus on collaborations in innovation development system, which account for contractual agreements (strategic partnerships, intellectual property licensing) and informal collaboration and knowledge exchange (working relationships of individuals across organizations)

⁷³ Wagner C. et al. (2005), ERAnets Evaluation of Networks of Collaboration among participants in IST Research and their evolution to Collaborations in the European Research Area

⁷⁴ 21'th Century Innovation Working Group (2004), Working Group Final Report, Council of Competitiveness in the National Innovation Initiative, Washington DC

- **Conditions for innovation** development is another potentially new indication field. Economic demand, public policy environment, infrastructure, social attitudes and cultural factors are critical for successful innovation.

The other characteristic feature of modern innovation phenomenon is importance of its market pull character. Innovation market determinant (marketable results -commercialization) criteria appeared as early as in J. Schumpeter works. Where as the commercialization criteria can be not true in some cases of the innovation development (open source models), general market determinant (and its pull character) stands in force. The market character of the innovation brings its Keynesian dimension as to innovation results implementation. In the case of Open Source the results do not have to be commercialized, the remuneration for the time spent on the project also does not have a tangible value. This is one of the reasons why the understanding for such mechanisms as knowledge exchange and networking must be developed.

Rapid increase in the focus on the innovation topic as a key to survival and success in the new knowledge economy has impacted economic policy in many countries.

Innovation policy initiatives has been recently undertaken by many national governments as well as international organizations of which major players include the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development, the European Commission, United Nations agencies, the World Economic Forum, and the World Bank.

One could risk a sentence that, the focus on the innovation has become so popular among the policy decision makers nowadays, that it has become a certain manifestation of the innovation in the policy making processes itself.

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Appendixes

Appendix I
Type and degree of novelty and the definition of innovation

			INNOVATION			<i>Not Innovation</i>
			Maximum	Intermediate	Minimum	
			New to the world	(a)	New to the firm	
INNOVATIONS	Technologically new	Product				
		Production process				
		Delivery process				
	Significantly technologically improved	Product				
		Production process				
		Delivery process				
Other Innovation	New or improved	Purely organisation				
<i>Not Innovation</i>	No Significant change, Change without novelty, Creative improvements	Product				
		Production process				
		Delivery process				
		Purely organisation				

TPP innovation Other innovation Not innovation
(a) Could be geographical e.g. new to the country or region

Source: OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

Appendix II

Scope and impact of technological innovation and innovation activity of enterprise

Technological innovations comprise implemented technologically new products and process and significant technological improvements in product and process.

An innovation has been implemented if it has been introduced on the market (product innovation) or used within a production process (process innovation). The product or process should be new (or significantly improved) to the enterprise (it does not necessarily have to be new to the relevant market).

Innovation activities are all those steps necessary to develop and implement technologically new or improved products

Technological innovation requires and objective improvement in the performance of a product or in the way in which it is produced or delivered. The following changes are not technological innovations:

- improvements of products that make them more attractive to the purchasers without changing their 'technological' characteristics
- minor technological changes of products and processes or changes which do not have the sufficient degree of novelty
- changes of products and processes, where the novelty does not concern the use or objective performance characteristics of the products or the way they are produced or delivered, but rather their aesthetic or subjective qualities

▶ A technologically new product is the product whose technological characteristics or intended uses differ significantly from those of previously produced products. Such innovations can involve radically new technologies, can be based on combining existing technologies in new uses, or can be delivered from the use of new knowledge.

▶ A technologically improved product is an existing product whose performance has been significantly enhanced or upgraded. A simple product may be improved (in terms of better performance or lower costs) through use of higher –performance components or materials, or a complex product, which consists of, a number of integrated technical subsystems, may be improved by partial changes to one of the subsystems.

Defining technological innovation – Community Innovation Survey (CIS)
Source: CIS-2 Questionnaire

1997 Oslo Manual Definition based

Appendix III

Strengths and Weaknesses of Measures of Inventive and Innovative Activities

Measure	Strengths	Weaknesses	Possible Levels of Comparison			
			Country	Industry	Tech Field	Firm
RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular and recognised data on main source of technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lacks details (technical fields and specific firms) Strongly underestimates small firms, design, production engineering, and software 	YES	YES	NO	YES
PATENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular details and long-term data Compensates weaknesses of R&D 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uneven propensity to patent Misses software 	YES	YES	YES	YES
SIGNIFICANT INNOVATIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct measure output 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measure of significance Cost of collection Misses incremental improvements 	NO	YES	NO	YES
EXPERT JUDGEMENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct use of expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finding independent experts Judgements beyond expertise 	?	YES	YES	NO
PRODUCT ANNOUNCEMENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Close to commercialisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Misses in-house process innovations, and incremental product improvements Possible manipulation by marketing and public relations 	?	YES	NO	YES
TECHNICAL EMPLOYEES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measures tacit knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of homogeneity of qualifications 	NO	YES	YES	YES
ACTUAL vs PREDICTED MARKET VALUE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tries to measure firms' efficiency in asset exploitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cannot distinguish innovation from other intangible assets, or from monopoly Difficult to make international comparisons 	?	YES	NO	YES

Source: Calvert, J, Ibarra, C, Patel, P, Pavitt K and Von Tunzelmann, N. (1996), Innovation Outputs in European Industry: Analysis from CIS, Brighton: Science Policy Research Unit

Appendix IV Innovation Definition Comparison

DEFINITION source	Object			Process			Subject				Results				Timeframe	
	Technological Product (goods and services) and Process (TPP)	Generally Product and Process	Not defined	New implementations	Improvements	Not defined	Private sector – economic based	Generally institution - include PA and NGOs	General - world-wide economy, nation	Not defined	Value creation for stakeholders, higher standard of living	General economic growth	General product application	Not Defined	Defined -period under review	Not defined
Community rules on state aid for innovation SEC(2004) 1453	X			X	X		X							X	X	
European Innovation Scoreboard 2004 European Commission COM (1995) 688 (Green Paper on Innovation)		X		X	X				X					X		X
COM (2003) 112 final		X		X	X			X						X		X
Innovation in FP7 INFSO Position Paper (2004)		X		X	X		X	X						X		X
Polish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Labour (2000)	X			X	X				X					X		X
Oslo Manual (1997)	X			X	X		X							X	X	
NII 21 st Century Innovation Working Group (2004)		X		X	X			X		X	X					X
US Department of Commerce NIST GCR 02–841 (2003)		X		X	X			X				X				X

US definitions OECD-EU definition EU definitions

Appendix V Innovation Concept Development Timeline

INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION ERA

INFORMATION REVOLUTION ERA

INVENTION ERA

INNOVATION CONCEPTUALIZATION

INNOVATION ENCHANCEMENT POLICIES

Organization and management innovation theories
- J. Taylor
- M. Webber

1990's –
The Network economy
ICT importance

1997 –
E. Raymond –
Open Source Model conceptualization
ICT Network innovation domination

1911 –
J. Schumpeter
Economic
Development

1956 –
R. Sollow and
Swan
Neoclassical
model of Growth

1986 –
P. Romer
Endogenous Growth
Model

Kline and Rosenberg
Innovation Chain-link
model

Rapid
internet
expansion

R&D and Innovation as key elements in
knowledge-based economy:
- (1994 – 2013) IST in FP4 – FP7
- 1994 IV Frascati Manual
- 1997 Oslo Manual
- New means of measuring innovation:
- knowledge, networks, environment

XIX 1910

1950

1980

1990

1995

2000

2005

Classic - supply side economy

1950 –
Keynesian Era – demand side economy

Adam Smith
Entrepreneurship theories

P. Drucker
Knowledge worker